

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING AUTHENTIC TEXTS OF MASS MEDIA TO DEVELOP READING COMPETENCE

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Abstract

This paper intended to investigate the formation of high school students' reading competence using authentic texts of mass media. The study involved a total of 14 students of 10th grade in N110 school-gymnasium. Descriptive quantitative research method was employed to identify the students' attitudes towards the use of authentic texts of mass media as English reading material. The findings of the present study revealed that the majority of the students preferred reading authentic media texts (78%) more than non-authentic ones (22%). The findings of this study indicate that texts from mass media are helpful in fostering critical thinking abilities, knowledge, and cultural understanding. It is recommended that research on formation of reading competence should not stop from investigation and exploration in order to assist learners in becoming successful English language learners.

Keywords: reading competence, authentic texts, mass media, high school

1. Introduction

In Kazakhstan's secondary educational system, EFL students have poor reading skills. It is challenging for the students to comprehend the text's overall meaning because many words are hard for them to understand. As a result, they are no longer interested in reading texts written in foreign languages. Since reading proficiency among Kazakhstani EFL learners is the issue that needs to be addressed, the study will focus on the importance of authentic materials in this area.

Reading competence is significant in our country where English is taught as a foreign language because high-school students need this competence to obtain knowledge, to enlarge their English vocabulary and to acquire a variety of information and professional skills in their future academic world. However, ineffective reading materials that are used in English lessons are not relevant for the development of students' reading competence. Additionally, the lack of well-developed textbooks, newspapers in English, and engaging English-language books are the main barriers to the development of reading abilities (1).

In the era of modern digital technologies and the Internet, authentic media texts do not lose their popularity and are a means of teaching a foreign language to students of different levels. Authentic text has been defined as text created to serve a specific social purpose within a language community. Authentic materials are created for native speakers that we can use for learning purposes: words, phrases, and expressions heard and read in real life situations. Articles, interviews, reader letters to print newspapers, commentary, reportage, teen diary excerpts, advertisements, recipes, fairy tales, popular science, and local texts are considered as authentic materials (2). However, bringing a clipping from a foreign newspaper or magazine to the students is not sufficient, it is also necessary to make the process of working on the text authentic. This will help students see their work on the text not as an exercise, but rather as an authentic communicative activity, encouraging natural interaction in the classroom.

Teaching to read newspapers and magazines is an important task of language teaching, as it contributes to

a significant increase in motivation to master foreign languages and the development of speech skills. Learning to read foreign press in foreign language lessons contributes to the adaptation of schoolchildren to foreign language speech and culture. In addition, reading mass media texts gives students the opportunity to get up-to-date information about various spheres of life in the modern society of the country of the studied language, to find material that corresponds to their personal interests and hobbies. The information contained in the press solves the problems of interdisciplinary relations, activating knowledge of such academic disciplines as history, geography, natural sciences, literature, native language and other sciences. Since the language of the press reflects the dynamics of the development of society, it contributes to the development of new lexical units and modern language forms (3). Namaziandost et al. (4) examined the impact of the authentic versus non-authentic reading materials on the reading comprehension of EFL learners. The results revealed that authentic texts improved students' reading competence and motivation to reading. However, Miller (5) argues that non-authentic resources are those made explicitly for educational purposes, and that the language employed in them is artificial with a tendency toward well-formed sentences, which is excellent for teaching grammar. Some examples of non-authentic materials include student workbooks, textbooks, and course books.

Numerous studies (6) have been conducted to investigate the effect of authentic materials on learners' reading abilities. None of the previous research has examined the impact of authentic-based versus non-authentic-based materials on the reading competence of Kazakhstani EFL learners at the senior stage of secondary school.

This study aims to identify possibilities of using authentic texts of mass media as a reading material by conducting a questionnaire among 10th grade students. Specifically, this study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the attitudes of high school students in Kazakhstan towards the use of authentic texts of mass media as English reading material?
2. Do authentic texts help high school students increase their vocabulary and improve their reading comprehension?

2. Research method

The research was conducted in N110 school-gymnasium, to be more specific in one class of tenth-grade students. To fulfill the objectives of this study, 14 high school students were selected. All of the participants were native speakers of Kazakh language in the age ranging from 15 to 17 years old.

To evaluate the potential impact of using authentic reading sources for advancement of the students' reading skills, survey questions were prepared. Each question provided five options; strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. Results of the survey in a percentage rate will be introduced and discussed in the next section.

To investigate students' attitudes toward using news articles as supplementary English reading materials, students were taught to use news articles as reading supplements for three weeks (8 hours) before completing the survey. The students received the survey questions at the conclusion of the process. It includes two main sections. Survey devoted for this study takes the form of a set of written questions. The form of the questions is Yes/ No, multiple choice questions. Each of these sections contains from 5 to 8 questions that aim to draw out the learners' responses about the target area.

Data collection is analyzed in different ways according to the research tools that are used in this study. The researcher presented the analyzed data into illustrative explanation, individual responses and numerical data (pie-charts, bar-graphs) as far as quantitative analyses are concerned.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Results

Generally speaking, the results of the survey appeared to be compatible with the predictions made by the authors and the general theoretical frame of the current research.

In overall, the findings looked to be consistent with the author's predictions and the broad theoretical framework of the current study. The study's findings were documented by questions that were completed by senior secondary school students in the tenth grade.

Research question 1

The online questionnaire received 14 responses in total from seniors in secondary school (a 100% response rate). In the class, there are (57%) females and (43%) males. The study's findings showed that the majority of students (about 64% of all respondents) take pleasure in and enjoy studying English, while just 5 students (or 36% of all respondents) have little interest in the process. These 14 learners read authentic texts of mass media before completing a questionnaire. As a result, all responders understand what is meant by an authentic material and are able to distinguish between authentic and non-authentic texts. The majority of the learners responded positively towards the implementation of authentic texts in classroom. According to the respondents' answers, students (78%) prefer the use of authentic media texts in reading comprehension lessons, whereas some of the students (22%) disapprove of the idea of utilizing authentic texts in the classroom. Most learners (93%) are conscious of their learning, according to the findings. Their ability to understand English is being developed using this content. Additionally, mass media sources like magazines and newspapers are preferable among high school students. While taking into consideration the attitudes of high school students, using authentic texts of mass media can be a useful tool to help students strengthen their reading skills.

Pie-chart 1. Popular types of authentic materials among high school students

Research question 2

The appropriate response to each item is asked for on a five-point Likert scale in this section. The following bar graph displays the findings:

Bar graph 1. Learners' answers towards the use of newspaper texts on their performance

The results of the bar graph show that the majority of students (59%) agree that authentic texts of mass media are more efficient than non-authentic ones. Just 3% of students answered that authentic texts are ineffective. It is clear that students value authentic texts higher than non-authentic texts. At the same time, 48% of the participants agree authentic texts motivate learners to be exposed to more reading materials in English. Approximately 39, 44% of learners strongly agree and agree that reading mass media texts demonstrates and clarifies how English is used in the native community. The results show that students' reading is ability enhanced through the use of such type of texts, indicating the percentage in strongly agree and agree range from 30% to 43%. Taking into account the answers of the students, it can be noticed that students really benefit from vocabulary included in mass media texts. Additionally, the majority of students concur that texts from mass media are helpful in fostering critical thinking abilities, knowledge, and cultural understanding. "Do authentic texts help high school students increase their vocabulary and improve their reading comprehension?" can be answered using the study's findings as many students listed how using these materials can help them become better readers.

3.2. Discussion

This research tackles one of the most important teaching materials that EFL teachers can use in classroom. The exposure to reading authentic texts of mass media is the crucial aim of the present study for enhancing reading competence of students at the senior stage of secondary school. For that, 10th grade students in N110 school-gymnasium were taken as study population from which the sample is selected for this research to carry out the investigation.

The results from this study showed that the students' attitude towards news articles as English reading material was "agree." In particular, the majority of students strongly agreed that reading news article can improve their vocabulary. They also agreed that news articles were appropriate material for teaching reading in terms of improving reading comprehension skill, providing interesting and up-to-date content, providing authentic resources, providing for a deeper understanding about the lifestyles and cultures of native English-

speaking countries, and also helping to promote good relationships with their English teacher.

The second research question inquires about how can newspaper texts be beneficial for learners in improving reading skill and vocabulary? To answer this question, the researcher conducted students' questionnaire. The data collected via this tool showed that a significant achievement in the reading skill in each session of reading comprehension and written expression when students are exposed to newspaper texts with activities. Learners' vocabulary is gradually improving. The longer EFL learners are exposed to authentic newspaper texts, the more they read and learn vocabulary. Providing learners with extensive reading of newspaper texts may raise the sense of achievement in language learning, fluency in reading, words spelling...etc. The results of the study consistent with study of Begoña Oliveras (7), which studied the use of news article as a tool to develop critical thinking in science classes, suggesting that improvement in students' critical thinking skills came from both critical activities which the teacher organized as well as the appropriate materials containing different data, arguments, opinions, and evidence. Therefore, he used news article as a material and he also suggested teachers can use texts from various resources such as magazines and the internet.

There are certain limitations in the study as a result of the research's methodology, which may weaken the validity of the results. On the one hand, the questionnaire is insufficient, and this is because there isn't enough time. On the other side, there are not enough participants to obtain valid data. It is advised to conduct additional research on the usage of media texts in EFL classes based on the current research's findings. Here are some suggestions that could be considered for upcoming research. It would be preferable if a sizable number of students participated in the study.

4. Conclusion

The overall assessment of the study's findings revealed that using authentic materials in English teaching contributes to the development of reading competence of 10th grade students. Furthermore, it was identified that English classes conducted using newspapers and magazines were positively evaluated by the participating students. It was noted that students found authentic material similar to what they encounter in their

daily lives and stated that their reading ability improved as a result of using this type of text. It was discovered that students enjoyed reading more after being instructed and were more motivated to participate in these activities due to the use of authentic material.

References

1. Younas, Muhammad, et al. Role of ESL instructors and learners' attitude to use pedagogical techniques in developing reading skills at the secondary level: A case study of Lahore, Pakistan. *Al-Qalam*. 2019; 24(1): 411-425.
2. Serikova M. Zh. The role of socio-cultural competence in teaching a foreign language using linguistic and cultural realities. *KazUIR&WL after Ablaihan*. 2018; 91.
3. Harya T. D. The Influence of Using Printed Mass Media on the Students Reading Comprehension. *Attractive: Innovative Education Journal*. 2022;4(2):168–189.
4. Albiladi WS. Exploring the use of written authentic materials in ESL reading classes: Benefits and challenges. *English Language Teaching*. 2018;12(1):67.
5. Namaziandost, Ehsan, et al. "The impact of authentic materials on reading comprehension, motivation, and anxiety among Iranian male EFL learners." *Reading & Writing Quarterly* 38.1 (2022): 1-18.
6. Miller L. Developing listening skills with authentic materials. *ESL Magazine*. 2003;6 (1): 16-19.
7. Oliveras B, Márquez C, Sanmartí N. The use of newspaper articles as a tool to develop critical thinking in science classes. *International Journal of Science Education*. 2013;35(6):885–905.